

High Performance Computing Enabled Through Neuromorphic Systems and In-Memory Computing Primitives

Aishwarya Natarajan

Artificial Intelligence Research Lab (AIRL), Hewlett Packard Labs, USA

Email: aishwarya.natarajan@hpe.com

Abstract—As data-driven workloads continue to grow, building computationally efficient hardware has become increasingly critical. Drawing inspiration from the brain, fundamental blocks of neurons and synapses are developed to create neuromorphic systems, which, along with approaches such as In-Memory Computing (IMC), can further enhance energy efficiency. We explore analog configurable platforms that facilitate real-time systems, as well as leverage IMC primitives like Analog Content Addressable Memories designed with emerging non-volatile technologies such as memristors, to show tree-based machine learning models. Together, these innovations pave the way for a holistic approach to constructing large-scale systems for high-performance computing.

Index Terms—Neuromorphic, Brain inspired, In-memory computing, Hodgkin-Huxley neuron, ODE solutions, CAM

I. HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTING

In a post-Moore’s law world coupled with the rising compute requirements of workloads in the areas of Machine learning, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), it is the need of the hour to explore emerging technologies and computational paradigms to achieve High Performance Computing (HPC). As we go beyond conventional Von Neumann architectures, neuromorphic computing [1] has a great potential to provide high energy efficiency as well as act as an alternative technique to implement brain-inspired systems [2], that govern both computational processing as well as memory in the same unit. Further, we can turn to analog In-Memory Compute based (IMC) architectures [3] and primitives to mitigate the expensive movement of data between memory and computational units which minimizes the constraints on the bandwidth, thereby offering an effective means to handle this Von Neumann bottleneck. Such approaches will help us scale up and offer massive parallelism to build the next generation of hardware accelerators to drive HPC based systems and run computationally intense applications (Fig. 1).

With just 20W of power [4], the human brain performs computations comparable with those done by supercomputers that consume megawatts of power. Neuromorphic computing is about translating these energy-efficient neural systems, as well as implementing competitive techniques, by understanding and exploiting the computational advantages of such structures.

Fig. 1. High performance computing is enabled through a heterogeneous hardware accelerator that is biologically inspired as well as implemented through analog and in-memory compute based primitives with emerging technologies such as memristors.

II. ANALOG AND NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEMS

Keeping such goals in mind, a reconfigurable and programmable device like a large-scale Field Programmable Analog Array (FPAA) [5], utilizing non-volatile structures called floating gates [6], significantly contributes to HPC based solutions. We have experimentally demonstrated the fundamental blocks of Hodgkin-Huxley neurons [7] and synapses [8] built from the Configurable Analog Blocks (CABs) (Fig. 2(a)) on an FPAA, fabricated on a 350-nm process [9]. The circuit has been inspired by the similarity between biology and silicon, by modelling ion channels and their time constants. This system is available to circuit designers [10] as well as to users in the neuroscience community [11]. Neuron models directly implemented in software [12] are much slower and far from real-time in terms of the model complexities. Fig. 2(b) shows the experimental silicon results on the action potential dynamics of a Hodgkin-Huxley neuron. Spiking neural networks [13] can be built from such compiled blocks [14] of channel based neurons and synapses [15] that remain true to the biophysics of neurons and perform compact low-power real-time computation [16] to execute a range of algorithms on hardware, handling the analog non-idealities and variations [17], [18] in a robust manner [19].

Another opportunity to leverage analog systems for HPC is to use such analog accelerators to help solve Ordinary Differ-

Analog and Neuromorphic computing on Reconfigurable FPAA

Fig. 2. (a) Configurable Analog Blocks (CABs) in FPAA which consist of transconductance amplifiers, floating gates etc. are used to compile and implement the desired algorithm. (b) Experimental measurements from the FPAA for an action potential from a Hodgkin-Huxley Neuron. (c) Dynamics for a compiled 8×8 A matrix to implement the ODE, $Ax=b$. Each of the eight nodes converges to their final steady state solution with different time-constants as expected.

ential Equations (ODEs). Solutions of linear systems through matrix decomposition are the most straight-forward methods for digital computation and yet are the most challenging option for analog approaches. We have experimentally demonstrated a programmable linear equation solver by analog computation [20]. A set of differential equations are solved using transconductance amplifiers on hardware by transforming the $Ax=b$ problem into an ODE. This approach opens the entire range of analog computing to HPC [21] by finding analog algorithmic solutions for linear systems. Fig. 2(c) shows the experimental dynamics for a compiled 8×8 A matrix through the matrix solution outputs, $x(t)$ which are the steady-state responses. Such analog-based solutions offer a $100\times$ area improvement and $350\times$ energy efficiency [21] compared to custom digital solutions.

III. IN-MEMORY COMPUTING PRIMITIVES

Furthermore, as the size of the models increases especially for Generative AI and transformer based workloads, we need to look beyond Complementary Metal-Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS) transistor based technologies to improve the throughput and energy efficiency of hardware accelerators. A variety of IMC based architectures [3] have been developed utilizing emerging non-volatile devices such as memristors or Resistive Random Access Memories (ReRAMs) [22] and have forecasted a high computational efficiency [23].

Fig. 3. (a) Decision tree from root to leaf node is mapped on an ACAM array and the classified outputs or leaves are stored in a RAM. (b) Classification outputs are recorded on the Match Lines for a feature input set from a 128×16 ACAM array in a parallel manner to achieve one-shot inference.

The design and use of a rapidly searchable memory structure, or a Content Addressable Memory (CAM), with a resistive memory technology allow the acceleration of a wide variety of tasks ranging from Regular expression matching [24] to machine learning tasks [25]. CAMs are highly useful in-memory computing primitives that give the location of the input data word, unlike traditional RAMs that return the contents of the corresponding input address. Analog CAMs (ACAM) [26] make use of the multi-bit level capabilities and full range of the ReRAM conductances that can be programmed. It can store a range of values and the cell indicates a match when the search value is within the cell's programmed range.

Decision trees (DT) perform well for tabular data [27] and help in achieving trustworthy AI through their explainability [28]. Fig. 3(a) shows a tree-based model implemented through an ACAM array. ACAMs are naturally suited to map DTs, as they can store discrete or continuous ranges corresponding to the feature and thereby one-shot inference can be done. The DT models are trained using eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [29], for binary classification on the churn dataset [30]. In the ACAM array, the columns are activated corresponding to the input features, while the cells are programmed with the trained weights [25]. The simulated results of the Match Lines (ML) [31] for a programmed DT from an ACAM array corresponding to a set of input features are plotted, and the accelerator produces the classification result in a single cycle (Fig. 3(b)).

IV. DISCUSSION

Our efforts in building neuromorphic systems as well as IMC based architectures lay the foundation to demonstrate physical systems and these techniques are vital steps towards demonstrating computationally energy-efficient systems. This enables one to create the next generation of hardware accelerators that will enable low-power, robust computing with a high throughput. Moreover, these brain-inspired systems represent the initial steps towards developing a high-performance supercomputer that leverages emerging technologies, aiming to approach the efficiency with which our brain processes information.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. A. Mead, "Neuromorphic electronic systems," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 78, p. 1629–1636, 1990.
- [2] C. Mead, *Analog VLSI and Neural Systems*. Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., 1989.
- [3] A. Sebastian, M. Le Gallo, R. Khaddam-Aljameh, and E. Eleftheriou, "Memory devices and applications for in-memory computing," *Nature nanotechnology*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 529–544, 2020.
- [4] J. Hasler and H. Marr, "Finding a roadmap to achieve large neuromorphic hardware systems," *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 7, p. 118, 2013.
- [5] J. Hasler, "Large-scale field-programmable analog arrays," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 108, no. 8, pp. 1283–1302, 2020.
- [6] P. E. Hasler, "Floating-gate devices, circuits, and systems, invited," in *Proceedings of the 5th IEEE International Workshop on System-on-Chip for Real-Time Applications (IWSOC 2005), 20-24 July 2004, Banff, Alberta, Canada*, pp. 482–487, 2005.
- [7] A. Natarajan and J. Hasler, "Hodgkin–huxley neuron and fpaa dynamics," *IEEE transactions on biomedical circuits and systems*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 918–926, 2018.
- [8] A. Natarajan and J. Hasler, "Implementation of synapses with hodgkin huxley neurons on the fpaa," in *2019 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pp. 1–5, May 2019.
- [9] S. George, S. Kim, S. Shah, J. Hasler, M. Collins, F. Adil, W. R., S. Nease, and S. Ramakrishnan, "A programmable and configurable mixed-mode fpaa soc," *IEEE Transactions on VLSI*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 2253–2261, 2016.
- [10] J. Hasler and A. Natarajan, "An open-source toolset for FPAA design," in *Article No. 18, Third Workshop on Open-Source EDA Technology (WOSET), 2020*.
- [11] A. Natarajan and J. Hasler, "Using soc fpaa and integrated simulator for implementation of circuits and systems in education," in *2017 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pp. 1–4, IEEE, 2017.
- [12] A. Natarajan and J. Hasler, "Modeling, simulation and implementation of circuit elements in an open-source tool set on the FPAA," *Analog Integrated Circuits and Signal Processing*, vol. 91, no. 1, pp. 119–130, 2017.
- [13] A. Dabbous, M. Mastella, A. Natarajan, E. Chicca, M. Valle, and C. Bartolozzi, "Artificial bio-inspired tactile receptive fields for edge orientation classification," in *2021 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 2021.
- [14] J. Hasler, A. Natarajan, and S. Kim, "Enabling energy-efficient physical computing through analog abstraction and ip reuse," *Journal of Low Power Electronics and Applications*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 47, 2018.
- [15] A. Natarajan and J. Hasler, "Dynamics of hodgkin huxley neuron across chips implemented on a reconfigurable platform," in *2018 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pp. 1–5, 2018.
- [16] A. Natarajan, *ANALOG AND NEUROMORPHIC COMPUTING WITH A FRAMEWORK ON A RECONFIGURABLE PLATFORM*. PhD thesis, Georgia Institute of Technology, 2021.
- [17] S. Shah, H. Toreyin, J. Hasler, and A. Natarajan, "Temperature sensitivity and compensation on a reconfigurable platform," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 604–607, 2018.
- [18] S. Shah, H. Toreyin, J. Hasler, and A. Natarajan, "Models and techniques for temperature robust systems on a reconfigurable platform," *Journal of Low Power Electronics and Applications*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. 21, 2017.
- [19] A. Natarajan and J. Hasler, "Built-in self-test of vector matrix multipliers on a reconfigurable device," in *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 2020.
- [20] A. Natarajan and J. Hasler, "Analog solutions of systems of linear equations on a configurable platform," in *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 2020.
- [21] J. Hasler and A. Natarajan, "Continuous-time, configurable analog linear system solutions with transconductance amplifiers," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 765–775, 2020.
- [22] X. Sheng, C. E. Graves, S. Kumar, X. Li, B. Buchanan, L. Zheng, S. Lam, C. Li, and J. P. Strachan, "Low Conductance and Multilevel CMOS Integrated Nanoscale Oxide Memristors," *Advanced Electronic Materials*, vol. 5, p. 1800876, Sept. 2019.
- [23] M. Hu, C. E. Graves, C. Li, Y. Li, N. Ge, E. Montgomery, N. Davila, H. Jiang, R. S. Williams, J. J. Yang, Q. Xia, and J. P. Strachan, "Memristor-Based Analog Computation and Neural Network Classification with a Dot Product Engine," *Advanced Materials*, vol. 30, p. 1705914, Mar. 2018.
- [24] C. E. Graves, S.-T. Lam, X. Li, L. Kiyama, M. Foltin, M. P. Hardy, J. P. Strachan, C. Li, X. Sheng, W. Ma, S. R. Chalamalasetti, D. Miller, J. S. Ignowski, B. Buchanan, and L. Zheng, "Memristor TCAMs Accelerate Regular Expression Matching for Network Intrusion Detection," *IEEE Transactions on Nanotechnology*, vol. 18, pp. 963–970, 2019.
- [25] G. Pedretti, C. E. Graves, S. Serebryakov, R. Mao, X. Sheng, M. Foltin, C. Li, and J. P. Strachan, "Tree-based machine learning performed in-memory with memristive analog CAM," *Nature Communications*, vol. 12, p. 5806, Oct. 2021.
- [26] C. Li, C. E. Graves, X. Sheng, D. Miller, M. Foltin, G. Pedretti, and J. P. Strachan, "Analog content-addressable memories with memristors," *Nature Communications*, vol. 11, p. 1638, Apr. 2020.
- [27] L. Grinsztajn, E. Oyallon, and G. Varoquaux, "Why do tree-based models still outperform deep learning on typical tabular data?," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 35, pp. 507–520, 2022.
- [28] S. M. Lundberg, G. Erion, H. Chen, A. DeGrave, J. M. Prutkin, B. Nair, R. Katz, J. Himmelfarb, N. Bansal, and S.-I. Lee, "From local explanations to global understanding with explainable AI for trees," *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 2, pp. 56–67, Jan. 2020.
- [29] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System," in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, (San Francisco California USA), pp. 785–794, ACM, Aug. 2016.
- [30] S. Iyyer, "Churn modelling [online] available 2019," <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shrutimechlearn/churn-modelling>.
- [31] A. Natarajan, L. Buonanno, T. Richmond, D. Vickers, X. Sheng, J. Moon, D. Miller, G. Pedretti, C. Graves, and J. Ignowski, "Design space exploration of analog cam for tree-based models," in *2023 IEEE 66th International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, pp. 93–97, IEEE, 2023.